

EXPLORING STAKEHOLDERS' PERCEPTIONS OF BRIGADA ESKWELA AND ITS IMPACT ON KALAMTUKAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the significance of the Brigada Eskwela (BE) program at Kalamtukan Elementary School, focusing on stakeholders' engagement, satisfaction, and the resulting improvements. The participants included 15 teachers, 30 students, 30 parents, 30 community members, and 30 local officials. A researcher-made questionnaire assessed the stakeholders' perceptions of the BE program's impact on school facilities, student performance and engagement, the learning environment, community participation and satisfaction, and the sustainability of improvements. The findings revealed that all participants were very active in the BE initiatives. The stakeholders perceived the school facilities and learning environment as excellent, with significant improvements in students' performance and engagement due to Brigada Eskwela. The results also indicated very high satisfaction with the school improvements and a very high level of community engagement during the program's implementation. Furthermore, the stakeholders believed in the long-term sustainability of these improvements and noted the positive impact of the National Brigada Eskwela Hall of Fame Award on the community's perception of the school. The BE program was found to be highly successful, well-received, and impactful. Consequently, it is recommended to continuously promote strong community relationships and stakeholder engagement. Additionally, implementing a monitoring and evaluation system to assess the long-term impact of the improvements and identify areas needing further attention is suggested.

Keywords: *Brigada Eskwela (BE), Program Implementation, Community Engagement, Stakeholders, School Facilities*

INTRODUCTION

Community engagement is essential for eliminating barriers to quality education. Though external problems like low enrollment are identifiable, the community's reflective analysis of its unique circumstances leads to sustainable, locally generated solutions. Effective engagement empowers communities to support education in various ways, including school management and curriculum development. ("First Principles: Community Engagement in Education Programs Compendium," n.d.). Bekalu (2011), likewise, posited that community participation is a key factor in enhancing access to and the quality of education in a country. Additionally, schools often struggle to adapt to changes or implement necessary program improvements without active involvement from the community in various aspects (Bekalu, 2011).

Public schools in the Philippines face challenges in getting the community involved in their programs. At the beginning of each school year, they often struggle with the lack of support and cooperation from parents and other stakeholders. To address this issue, the Brigada Eskwela (BE) program, also known as National Maintenance Week, was launched in May 2003 (Brigada Eskwela Manual, 2009). This program exemplifies successful collaboration between schools and communities. One of the main hurdles is for school administrators to effectively communicate their efforts to the public in order to gain community support for improving education (DO 21, s. 2011). Indeed, Carmelo (2022) emphasized the importance of forming school-community partnerships, involving administrators, teachers, and students, to effectively implement programs like Brigada Eskwela. Such collaborations not only provide valuable resources but also help schools save costs. The ongoing support and efforts from various stakeholders have resulted in better learning environments and enhanced school facilities, ready for use at the beginning of the academic year. Consequently, students can now focus on their studies from the first day of classes without the distraction of preparing their classrooms.

Various Filipino scholars have explored the implementation of the BE (Brigada Eskwela) program in different schools in the country. Nieva (2023), for instance, focused on BE program implementation by school sizes and found that the majority of participants recognized the significant contributions made by stakeholders and appreciated the active involvement of private partners in the school. Requina (2022), on the other hand, investigated the level of compliance with the BE program implementation, while Legal et al. (2024) looked into the approaches that public school teachers used to ensure effective implementation of the BE program during the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, Garcia (2021) explored the best practices in implementing the BE program and stated that Brigada Eskwela is characterized by its collaborative nature, fostering a spirit of volunteerism and encouraging individuals from various sectors to assist schools annually and that it enhances community support for basic education by moderately enriching curricular activities and improving physical facilities, while significantly promoting a unified purpose in support of basic education.

However, this study specifically focuses on the Brigada Eskwela initiatives of Kalamtukan Elementary School in Bayawan City, Negros Oriental, which initiated its BE program in

2013. Before the program was implemented, the school faced challenges such as insufficient resources, lack of community engagement, and coordination and sustainability issues for its school initiatives. Nonetheless, in 2015, the school received the prestigious National Brigada Eskwela Hall of Fame Award and its BE program has been successful in recent years. However, the current researcher believes it is still important to continuously monitor and evaluate the BE program to maintain consistent community participation and educational improvement. The study focuses on understanding how stakeholders perceive the effectiveness of the BE program in enhancing the school. No previous local studies have explored the perspectives of parents, students, teachers, community members, and local officials regarding the BE program, which is why this study was undertaken.

Thus, the main purpose of the study is to collect feedback from stakeholders about their thoughts on the school's BE program and how it has contributed to enhancing school facilities and the learning environment. This feedback is essential for maintaining the success of the BE program.

Research Questions

This inquiry aims to gather the perceptions of Kalamtukan Elementary School's stakeholders regarding the Brigada Eskwela program implementation, community involvement, and the program's impact on the school's improvement. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How active are the following stakeholders in engaging in the school's BE program:
 - 1.1 Teachers;
 - 1.2 Students;
 - 1.3 Parents;
 - 1.4 Community Members; and
 - 1.5 Local Officials?
2. What is the impact of the BE program on the school, as perceived by the stakeholders, in terms of:
 - 2.1 School Facilities;
 - 2.2 Student Performance and Academic Engagement; and
 - 2.3 Overall Learning Environment?
3. What is the level of community involvement and support and level of satisfaction during the Brigada Eskwela?
4. What are the stakeholders' perceptions of the long-term sustainability of the improvements resulting from the Brigada Eskwela?
5. What is the impact of the National Brigada Eskwela Hall of Fame Award on the community's perception of Kalamtukan Elementary School as perceived by the stakeholders?

METHODOLOGY

Research design

This study utilized the descriptive method of research to achieve its objectives. This approach was instrumental in assessing the stakeholders' perceptions of the Brigada Eskwela (BE) program, its impact on Kalamtukan Elementary School, and the extent of community engagement throughout the program's implementation. By employing this method, the study provided ample account of the stakeholders' views and measured how the program impacted the school facilities and fostered community involvement.

Population and sampling

The participants for this study were chosen using the simple random sampling technique. This method guarantees that each person in the population has an equal chance of being selected for the sample (Acharya et al., 2013). In this study, the selection process involved using a table of random numbers. A total of 135 participants—15 teachers, 30 students, 30 parents, 30 community members, and 30 local officials—were selected.

Research instrumentation

The "Brigada Eskwela Impact and Effectiveness Survey" is a questionnaire created by the researcher as the main tool for gathering data in this study. The first part of the questionnaire collects information about the participants. The second part contains questions aimed at measuring the level of community engagement, the participants' perceptions of the program's contribution to improving the school's facilities and learning environment, and the level of their satisfaction with the support given by other members of the community (i.e. volunteers, local organizations, and businesses). Moreover, the questionnaire underwent review by three experts to ensure its contents' validity. A trial run was also conducted to confirm the reliability of the questionnaire's items. The results of the trial run, using Cronbach's alpha, showed alpha values of 0.7 and above, indicating that all items are reliable.

Data gathering procedures and analysis

Before distributing the questionnaires widely, a pilot test was conducted with a small group of teachers, students, parents, community members, and local officials. This step ensured the questions were clear and relevant. Adjustments were made based on feedback, and the survey was then distributed as paper forms during and after Brigada Eskwela events. Anonymity was also assured to encourage honest feedback from the participants. Moreover, efforts were made to include a diverse and representative sample from various roles within the school community.

After data collection, quantitative data were analyzed using statistical methods to identify trends. The results were then compiled into a comprehensive report that details the methodology, key findings, and actionable recommendations. This report was shared with stakeholders, including school administrators, local education authorities, and community leaders, to guide future Brigada Eskwela initiatives, ensuring they meet community needs and expectations.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the participants' profile information as regards their role during the Brigada Eskwela.

Table 1. Stakeholders' Profile

Profile (Role/Position)	Frequency	Percentage
Teachers	15	11.2
Students	30	22.2
Parents	30	22.2
Community Members	30	22.2
Local Officials	30	22.2
Total	135	100.0

It can be seen from the data that teachers have the lowest number of participants, while there are equal numbers of participants among students, parents, community members, and local officials.

Level of Stakeholders' Engagement and Participation

Table 2 reveals the participants' perceptions of how active they are in the Brigada Eskwela.

Table 2 Stakeholders' Participation and Engagement Level

Participants	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
Teachers	3.93	Very Active
Students	3.77	Very Active
Parents	3.90	Very Active
Community Members	3.73	Very Active
Local Officials	3.97	Very Active
Average	3.86	Very Active

Legend: 3.26-4.00 - Very Active; 2.51-3.25 - Moderately Active; 1.76-2.50 - Minimally Active; 1.00-1.75 - Not Involved

The data in Table 2 indicate that all the stakeholders participated very actively in the BE program. In particular, teachers, parents, and local officials have the highest levels of engagement as signified by the mean values of 3.93, 3.90, and 3.97, respectively.

Impact of Brigada Eskwela on Education

Table 3 presents data identifying how the Brigada Eskwela has contributed to the improvement of Kalamtukan Elementary School specifically in terms of school facilities, students' academic performance and engagement, and overall learning environment.

Table 3 School Facilities and Educational Improvement during the Brigada Eskwela

Areas	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
School Facilities		
Teachers	5.00	Excellent
Students	5.00	Excellent
Parents	5.00	Excellent
Community Members	4.97	Excellent
Local Officials	4.97	Excellent
Average	4.99	Excellent
Student Performance & Academic Engagement		
Teachers	4.87	Significantly Improved
Students	4.87	Significantly Improved
Parents	4.93	Significantly Improved
Community Members	4.83	Significantly Improved
Local Officials	4.93	Significantly Improved
Average	4.98	Significantly Improved
Overall Learning Environment		
Teachers	5.00	Excellent
Students	5.00	Excellent
Parents	5.00	Excellent
Community Members	4.97	Excellent
Local Officials	4.90	Excellent
Average	4.97	Excellent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 - Excellent/Significantly Improved; 3.41-4.20 - Good/Improved; 2.61-3.40 - Fair/No Noticeable Change; 1.81-2.60 - Poor/Declined; 1.00-1.80 - No Change Observed/Unsure

The results in Table 3 show that all stakeholders believe that the school facilities are excellent as signified by the average mean of 4.99. They also think that the students' performance and academic engagement have improved significantly, with an average mean of 4.98, because of the Brigada Eskwela. Furthermore, they perceive the overall learning environment to be excellent, with an average mean of 4.97, due to the program

implementation.

Level of Community Engagement and Stakeholders' Satisfaction

Table 4 presents the level of community involvement and the participants' satisfaction with the support provided by local businesses, organizations, and volunteers during the Brigada Eskwela activities.

Table 4 Community Involvement and Satisfaction Level during the Brigada Eskwela

Areas	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
Community Involvement and Support		
Teacher	4.93	Very High
Students	4.90	Very High
Parents	5.00	Very High
Community Members	4.83	Very High
Local Officials	4.97	Very High
Average	4.93	Very High
Satisfaction with the Support from Local Businesses, Organizations, and Volunteers		
Teachers	4.80	Very Satisfied
Students	4.77	Very Satisfied
Parents	4.83	Very Satisfied
Community Members	4.67	Very Satisfied
Local Officials	4.70	Very Satisfied
Average	4.75	Very Satisfied

Legend: 4.21-5.00 - Very High/ Very Satisfied; 3.41-4.20 - High/Satisfied; 2.61-3.40 - Moderate/Neutral; 1.81-2.60 - Low/Dissatisfied; 1.00-1.80 - None/Very Dissatisfied

The data indicate that there is a very high level of community involvement and support during the Brigada Eskwela as perceived by all the stakeholders. The stakeholders also claimed to be very satisfied with the support they have received from local organizations, businesses, and volunteers. It must be noted as well that among the stakeholders, the parents gave the highest ratings both in the areas of community involvement and satisfaction level.

Perceptions of Stakeholders on Sustainability

Table 5 provides data signifying the participants' views of the sustainability of the Brigada Eskwela's positive outcomes.

Table 5 Stakeholders' Perceptions of the Long-Term Sustainability of the Improvements Brought by the Brigada Eskwela

Participants	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
Teachers	3.93	Yes, definitely
Students	3.80	Yes, definitely
Parents	3.73	Yes, definitely
Community Members	3.80	Yes, definitely
Local Officials	3.73	Yes, definitely
Average	3.80	Yes, definitely

Legend: 3.26-4.00 - Yes Definitely; 2.51-3.25 - Yes, to some extent; 1.76-2.50 - Not sure; 1.00-1.75 - No, not sustainable

Table 5 reflects the participants' perceptions as to whether the improvements brought on by the Brigada Eskwela initiatives are sustainable or not in the long run. It is quite clear, based on the average mean of 3.80, that all the participants have a strong belief in the long-term sustainability of the BE program's positive impact on Kalamtukan Elementary School.

National Brigada Eskwela Hall of Fame Award and Its Impact on Community's Perception of Kalamtukan Elementary School

Table 6 presents evidence of the stakeholders' views of how the National Brigada Eskwela Hall of Fame Award, received by Kalamtukan Elementary School, has affected how the community perceives the school.

Table 6. Assessment of the Participants' Perceptions of the Impact of the National Brigada Eskwela Hall of Fame Award on Community Perception

Participants	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
Teachers	5.00	Very Positive
Students	5.00	Very Positive
Parents	5.00	Very Positive
Community Members	4.93	Very Positive
Local Officials	5.00	Very Positive
Average	4.99	Very Positive

Legend: 4.21-5.00 - Very Positively; 3.41-4.20 - Positively; 2.61-3.40 - No Noticeable Impact; 1.81-2.60 - Negatively; 1.00-1.80 – Unsure

The data show that, overall, the stakeholders believe that the National Brigada Eskwela Hall of Fame Award has a very positive impact on the community's perception of Kalamtukan Elementary School, as evidenced by the average mean of 4.99. Specifically, the teachers, students, parents, and local officials gave a perfect rating of 5.00. Only the community members gave a rating of 4.93.

DISCUSSION

Level of Stakeholders' Engagement and Participation

Notably, the teachers, parents, and local officials exhibited the highest engagement levels, which indicates a strong commitment from these groups. This result highlights the crucial roles of teachers, parents, and local officials in the successful implementation of the program. Their active involvement is essential for fostering a collaborative environment, ensuring that the objectives of Brigada Eskwela are effectively met and sustained. This is strengthened by the statements of Cando, as cited by Requina (2018), who found that the success of the Brigada Eskwela program depends on the commitment of school professionals, the cooperation of parents, the backing of the community, and the discipline of students to participate in volunteer activities. The program seeks volunteers willing to contribute their time, effort, and energy towards enhancing the school's infrastructure. Results from the study of Jungay and Guillo (2019), likewise, demonstrated that stakeholder volunteerism consistently remains at a high level.

Brigada Eskwela's Impact on Education

The high average mean of 4.99 indicates that the stakeholders unanimously consider the school facilities to be excellent, which is attributed to the effectiveness of the Brigada Eskwela program in improving physical infrastructure. Additionally, with an average mean of 4.98, the stakeholders believe that the program has significantly enhanced the students' performance and academic engagement, suggesting that improved facilities may positively impact educational outcomes. Lastly, the average mean of 4.97 for the overall learning environment implies that the Brigada Eskwela has created a conducive and supportive atmosphere for learning, which the stakeholders perceive as excellent. All these findings underscore the program's comprehensive impact on the school's educational quality and community involvement.

Similarly, Oco's study (2023) stresses the importance of a safe and adequate learning environment in enhancing students' performance, satisfaction, and participation in school activities and projects. Achieving this requires active stakeholder involvement, as the school staff alone cannot meet all the school's needs. Therefore, it is essential for school leaders to understand and implement strategies that attract volunteers, donors, and participants. On the same note, Nieva and Lim (2023) concluded that children with engaged parents exhibit notable improvements in academic performance, personality development, and participation in school activities, although these ideal conditions are often not seen in public secondary schools in other districts. They also revealed that Brigada Eskwela united community members to refurbish public schools in preparation for the new school year. During the week-long event, volunteers focused on tasks such as minor repairs, painting, and cleaning school campuses. Correspondingly, the data obtained by Andal et al. (2016) show that safe learning facilities achieved the highest level of implementation among the six provisions. This demonstrates that schools and educational partners prioritize and effectively focus their efforts on ensuring safe learning environments for students. It is reassuring to see that the safety and welfare of learners

are paramount for schools and their partners.

Level of Community Engagement and Stakeholders' Satisfaction

The findings underscore the success of Brigada Eskwela in fostering a strong sense of community and collective effort in supporting local schools. The high levels of involvement and support suggest that the program effectively mobilizes resources and engages various community members, including local organizations, businesses, and volunteers. This broad-based participation likely enhances the program's impact, ensuring that schools are well-prepared and maintained for the academic year. Moreover, the high satisfaction levels reported by stakeholders reflect the program's effectiveness in meeting their expectations and needs. This satisfaction likely contributes to sustained engagement and support from the community, as satisfied participants are more likely to continue their involvement in future initiatives. The positive feedback from local organizations and businesses indicates that these entities see value in their contributions, which can lead to more robust and long-term partnerships.

In addition, the fact that parents gave the highest ratings in both community involvement and satisfaction levels emphasizes the critical role they play in the program's success. Parents' active participation and high satisfaction suggest that they are highly invested in the education and welfare of their children, and they perceive the Brigada Eskwela as a valuable initiative that benefits the school and, by extension, their children. This strong parental involvement can have a positive ripple effect, encouraging other community members to participate and support the program. According to Cortez, as cited by Catid (2022), Brigada Eskwela was the school program with the highest participation from stakeholders, including parents, volunteers, and students. Parents played a particularly significant role, serving as observers and collaborators.

Perceptions of Long-Term Sustainability

The participants generally believe in the long-term sustainability of the improvements achieved through Brigada Eskwela initiatives at Kalamtukan Elementary School. The average mean score of 3.80 suggests a strong consensus among stakeholders that the positive changes brought about by the program will endure over time. This reflects confidence in the program's ability to maintain and support the school's enhanced facilities and learning environment, ensuring continued benefits for future students and the broader community. Resource mobilization was robust, with financial contributions amounting to 1,400,000.00 pesos and substantial material donations including paints, lumber, and other supplies. The involvement of 1,004 volunteers during the Brigada maintenance week underscored the community's dedication and support. Detailed reporting to DepEd ensured transparency and accountability, showcasing the tangible outcomes achieved through the initiative. Certainly, community involvement and support were pivotal in sustaining the initiative's success. Volunteers played a crucial role in executing tasks and maintaining the improvements, fostering a sense of ownership and pride among stakeholders. Partnerships with local businesses and organizations not only provided essential resources but also strengthened community ties and ensured ongoing

support for future endeavors.

Impact of National Brigada Eskwela Hall of Fame Award on the Community's Perception of Kalamtukan Elementary School

The data reveal that the stakeholders overwhelmingly view the National Brigada Eskwela Hall of Fame Award as having a highly positive impact on the community's perception of Kalamtukan Elementary School, with an impressive average mean of 4.99. This high rating indicates strong support and appreciation from all groups involved. Specifically, teachers, students, parents, and local officials awarded the highest possible rating of 5.00, reflecting their complete endorsement of the award's benefits. The slightly lower rating of 4.93 from community members still signifies a strong endorsement, suggesting that while the award is well-regarded, there might be minor areas for further engagement or improvement.

The recognition affirmed the school's dedication to excellence and community engagement, setting a benchmark for educational institutions nationwide. The award underlined Kalamtukan Elementary School's leadership in innovative educational practices and its commitment to continuous improvement, inspiring other schools and communities to emulate its success in enhancing educational environments through collaborative efforts like Brigada Eskwela.

Conclusions

The Brigada Eskwela initiative at Kalamtukan Elementary School has proven to be a highly successful school innovation. It demonstrates substantial participation and active engagement from all involved parties, including teachers, students, parents, community members, and local officials. The improvements to school facilities were unanimously rated as excellent, and the initiative significantly boosted student performance and academic engagement. Community involvement was notably high, with strong satisfaction regarding the support received from local businesses and organizations. The improvements are viewed as sustainable in the long term, and the overall perception of the initiative is overwhelmingly positive, indicating a well-received and impactful program.

Recommendations

To sustain and build on this success, it is recommended to continue fostering strong community relationships and stakeholder engagement. Implementing a monitoring and evaluation system will help assess the long-term impact of the improvements and identify areas needing further attention. Expanding participation opportunities to include more community members and organizations can diversify and strengthen support. Additionally, enhancing communication and feedback mechanisms will ensure transparency and continuous improvement. Documenting and sharing best practices can promote knowledge exchange with other schools while providing training and capacity-building programs for teachers, parents, and community members will enable more effective contributions to future school improvement efforts. These steps will help ensure

the sustained success and positive impact of Brigada Eskwela at Kalamtukan Elementary School.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study meticulously considered ethical aspects to ensure respectful and responsible research involving various stakeholders of Kalamtukan Elementary School, including teachers, students, parents, community members, and local officials. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they were aware of the study's purpose and their involvement. Confidentiality was rigorously maintained by anonymizing responses to protect participants' identities. Participation was entirely voluntary, with individuals having the freedom to withdraw from the study at any stage without facing any negative consequences. The study also ensured fairness by accurately representing the perspectives of all stakeholders and avoiding any biases in reporting the findings. These ethical practices were crucial in upholding the integrity of the research and ensuring that the participants' rights and contributions were respected throughout the study.

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